

PSYCHO-METHODICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' MEDICAL THINKING ABILITIES

Bakayev Najmiddin

Associate Professor of the Department of
Fundamental Medical Sciences,
Asian International University

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These decrees and resolutions, as they are applied in all areas of science and technology, do not bypass the subject of "Latin language and fundamentals of medical terminology" in the teaching of foreign languages, including in universities that train medical personnel with higher education in our state.

ABSTRACT

This ambitious task is set out in a number of decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2789 dated February 17, 2017 "On measures to further improve the activities of the Academy of Sciences, the organization, management and financing of scientific research work", No. PQ-5117 dated May 19, 2021 "On measures to bring the popularization of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level", No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", as well as other regulatory legal acts related to this activity.

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The positive changes taking place in the world of medicine, the modern demand for the introduction of new innovative technologies in the education and upbringing of future doctors, and the active use of modern medical equipment by our doctors in their professional activities, naturally lead to the introduction of new medical terms.

Mastering the profession of a future doctor is carried out with the perfect study of the professional language, as well as the comprehensive mastery of professional concepts and the wealth of terms that express them.

Medical terminology in the current era of globalization is literally a vast and complex

system of terms, encompassing several thousand terms. A distinctive feature of medical terminology is the use of the "traditional" medical Latin language, which has been around for centuries.

It is known that in the education and upbringing of young students studying in medical universities, thinking is the basis for the development and improvement of their comprehensive positive thinking skills, and its source is knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, the scientific and methodological analysis of thinking from an educational and educational perspective is extremely important in the development of young students' medical professional thinking skills.

Thinking is a form of generalized and conceptualized reflection of the human mind, which is complex and provides for the existence of mutual connections between things and phenomena that are considered objects of knowledge. The problems of thinking have long been beyond the reach of psychologists, educators and methodologists due to their complexity, and have been considered mainly as a matter of thought for philosophers and logicians.

Thinking allows us to understand the laws of the material world, the cause-and-effect relationships in nature and socio-historical life, and the laws of the human psyche. Practice, which is the field of application of the results of mental activity, serves as a source of thinking activity.

Thinking, like other cognitive processes, has its own individual characteristics, which are expressed in the different manifestations of the forms, means and relations of operations of thinking activity in people. Usually, the individual characteristics and qualities of thinking include the content of cognitive activity, independence, agility, efficiency, breadth, speed, depth of thought, and other qualities.

Individual differences in the thinking activity of people can be expressed in such qualities as thoroughness of thinking, breadth of thinking, depth and independence, flexibility of thought, initiative and criticality of the mind, logic, proof and creativity.

The transition to thinking allowed a person to overcome the limitations of direct sensory cognition. Thinking expresses a higher and qualitatively new level of rational cognition (Latin *rationalis* - rational).

Thought is the object of study of many disciplines, which analyze it from different sides and from different points of view. Philosophy studies thought in relation to being. First of all, psychology studies thinking as a real mental activity of a given subject, how thinking arises and develops, its structure, how it interacts with various types of activity, with other aspects of consciousness and personality traits, and what results it produces.

Thinking is the interaction of the subject with the objective world, starting from a problematic situation, and proceeding through analytical and synthetic activity, with the perceived object, that is, with the objectified system of knowledge.

Thinking is a specific type of theoretical and practical activity, which involves a system of actions and operations of a discovery, transformation, and cognitive nature. Thinking has its own qualitative content and manifestations.

When it comes to developing innovative thinking skills in Latin lessons, there are many students with different interests that only manifest themselves in certain circumstances. Their identification is mainly determined by factors such as emotions and motives, which are

not formed simultaneously with intellectual aptitude and do not allow students to develop their abilities to the highest level.

In the current educational environment, it is very important to create an environment that stimulates students' behavior and cognitive activity in Latin lessons to develop professional thinking skills of future medical students, which mainly affects teaching methods and active participation of students. The first step is to select appropriate tasks, taking into account the individual needs, abilities and talents of students. This task represents the entire structure that requires knowledge of the individual elements, processes, program justification, project objectives and results; they must participate in the formation of a holistic, logical and clearly presented correct solution. Each task consists of a stage of problem study; it identifies the steps leading to the solution, justifies the actions and determines the final results. This refers to the educational tasks associated with teaching - this is learning, the basis of which is the process of developing students' thinking skills. In this regard, the task of higher education institutions and teachers is to prepare the appropriate medical material and technical base so that the student has access to various materials, interesting information, necessary tools, and medical technical equipment.

The development of medical thinking skills in Latin lessons is one of the main tasks in the process of technical education. Medical technical training allows teachers to implement a wide range of creative activities for teaching. It is not limited to tasks alone, but should focus on the formation of attitudes and a culture of medical thinking, taking into account the cognitive activity and interests of students. In Latin lessons, the proper development of students' medical thinking skills is possible due to their innovative thinking and creative approach. For this, it is important for the teacher to pay attention to the selection of appropriate tasks and take a number of practical measures.

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